

Simple methods of extracting boron for assay of available soil boron

M. T. Cayton, research assistant; and F. N. Ponnampertuma, principal soil chemist, International Rice Research Institute

The standard method of extracting available boron from soils involves refluxing soil samples with a dilute solution of barium chloride. Because this procedure is not applicable to routine soil testing in developing countries, two simpler methods of boron extraction were compared with the standard method.

The available boron content of 53 rice soils (pH, 3.5-8.0; organic carbon, 0.1-14%; available boron, 0.2-24 mg/kg) was correlated with the boron content of IR42 grown on these soils in the greenhouse. The soils were assayed by three methods:

1. Refluxing 20 g soil with 40 ml water containing 0.5 ml 10% barium chloride for 5 minutes in a round-bottom flask on an electric heating mantle, filtering the suspension, and measuring boron in the filtrate (the standard method);
2. Gently boiling 20 g soil with 40 ml water containing 0.5 ml 10% barium chloride in a 200-ml conical flask with a small funnel in the mouth for 5 minutes on a hot plate, filtering, and measuring boron in the filtrate (the hot plate method) and;
3. Shaking 10 g 80-mesh soil with 20 ml 0.05 N HCl in a 50-ml plastic bottle on a horizontal shaker for 5 minutes at 180 cycles/minute, filtering, and analyzing boron in the filtrate (the 0.05 N HCl method).

Boron in the extracts was estimated spectrophotometrically after color development by the curcumin-oxalic method.

Available boron by the two simple methods correlated highly with boron by the standard method:

hot plate boron vs standard boron	$r = 0.971^{**}$
0.05 N HCl boron vs standard boron	$r = 0.956^{**}$

Plant boron correlated highly with available soil boron by the three methods

plant boron vs standard boron	$r = 0.842^{**}$
plant boron vs hot plate boron	$r = 0.842^{**}$
plant boron vs 0.05 N HCl boron	$r = 0.909^{**}$

The acid-extractable boron correlated better with plant boron than did boron by the two other methods.

The new methods are simple, reliable, rapid, inexpensive, applicable to routine soil testing, and are as efficient as the standard method for soil boron extraction. Apart from its simplicity, the 0.05 N HCl method has an added advantage: it can also be used to determine available copper and zinc.

The critical limits for boron toxicity in rice soils are 5 mg/kg by the hot plate method and 4 mg/kg by the 0.05 N HCl method. ■

Rice-based cropping systems

Arthropod abundance in continuous vs biannual rice cropping systems

P. C. Pantua, research assistant; and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology Department, Cropping Systems Program, International Rice Research Institute

With year-round irrigation, a continuous rice cropping pattern popularly termed a *rice garden* offers maximum utilization of land. If the field area is less than 1.5 ha, 4 crops of early maturing rice/year can be grown, using family labor, by dividing the field into 13 plots, transplanted sequentially each week.

Because rice is found in all growth stages at any one time, continuous cropping would appear ideal for insect pest buildup. We measured populations of both insect pests and natural enemies without insecticide protection over 2 years (1978-79) at IRRI using insect-susceptible cultivars (IR1917 in 1978 and IET 3877 in 1979) in continuous (0.25-ha field) and biannual (0.5-ha field) systems.

We hypothesized three possible consequences of continuous cropping in terms of insect pest population buildup:

1. Continuous cropping would nullify the inherent cultural control offered by biannual cropping to break pest population cycles. Pest populations would multiply to epidemic numbers more rapidly than in the biannual system.
2. There would be no significant change in pest abundance due to continuous cropping because insect pests could

successfully span the periods between the biannual crops through migration from nearby fields planted at different times.

3. Pest populations would decline in continuous plantings because of a newly-found favorable advantage offered to natural enemies whose population buildup had previously been selectively held back in biannual croppings (perhaps through a lower capability to migrate). The precedent for this statement comes from the well-documented fact that biological control is more successful on perennial than on annual crops, and continuous cropping is similar to a perennial crop.

Each group of insect pests may respond differently to continuous cropping. Whorl maggot and rice bug, which have definite preferences for specific stages of rice, may greatly increase in continuous cropping. Brown and white-backed planthoppers, which are believed to be highly successful migrants, may already have attained their biotic potential in biannual cropping systems. The wide array of stem borer and leaf folder larval parasites currently known, but considered ineffective, may become highly abundant to check these pests.

Insect pest populations were highly similar over four cropping seasons in continuous and biannual cropping systems (Table 1). They were generally low in both systems — only whorl maggot and stem borers exceeded economic injury levels during the 2 years. Stem borers were more abundant in con-